

1 **An expression screen to identify genes important for trastuzumab resistance: Pou6f1.**

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6 We measured total transcription by RNA-sequencing in patients sensitive or resistant to treatment with
7 trastuzumab for HER2+ breast cancer for discovery of genes that confer or support resistance to
8 HER2-targeted therapies in humans. In this manuscript we describe identification of Pou6f1 as a
9 candidate gene product of the trastuzumab resistance gene expression signature.

10 Citations

11 1. Wu, D. and Dean, J., 2023. RNA exosome ribonuclease DIS3 degrades Pou6f1 to promote mouse
12 pre-implantation cell differentiation. Cell reports, 42(2).